

Soiling Study on Antireflective Coated Glass Samples and Antisoiling/Antireflective Coated Glass Samples

Gema San Vicente¹, Nuria German¹, Augusto Maccari², Aránzazu Fernández-García³ and Angel Morales¹

¹CIEMAT-PSA. Solar Concentrating Systems Unit. Avenida Complutense 40, Madrid 28040 Spain

²Archimede Solar Energy, voc. Flaminia Vetus, 88 Fraz. Villa San Faustino 06056, Massa Martana (PG) Italy

³CIEMAT-PSA. Solar Concentrating Systems Unit. Ctra. Senés km. 4, P.O. Box 44, 04200, Tabernas, Spain

^aCorresponding author: gema.sanvicente@ciemat.es

Abstract. Soiling processes in concentrated solar power (CSP) technology is a key point which implies large water consumption and high cost to minimize its impact in the energy production. The deposition of dust on reflectors and receivers causes important energy yield losses that are reduced by frequent cleaning of the solar field which means increasing the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), especially in arid and semi-arid regions with scarce water availability. In this study, antireflective (AR) coated flat borosilicate samples equals to those used in the commercial glass envelope tubes of parabolic-through receivers are outdoor exposed at Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA). The special rack used for the exposure allows the evaluation of soiling at different inclination angles and orientations. In addition, a hydrophobic antisoiling (AS) treatment was applied in half of the samples in order to study its effect. This work is included in one of the tasks of Horizon 2020 WASCOP project which aim is reducing water consumption in CSP plants. Results obtained show the important role played by the inclination angle in soiling, overall in periods with low rainfall as summer. After 4 months of outdoor exposure the experimental procedure was optimized through a complete cleaning of the samples. From this reset it was seen that the AS treatment seems to help to clean the samples more effectively.

INTRODUCTION

One of the well-known methods used to increase of efficiency in parabolic-through solar power plants is applying an antireflective (AR) coating on both sides of the glass tubes envelopes that increases the solar transmittance of glass around 5% and therefore the optical efficiency to the same extent [1]. This coating has a very low refractive index requirement that is achieved by introducing pores in its structure and this porous structure can act as a magnet for the dust and soiling deposition. The impact of dust deposition in solar energy systems is so critical that an avalanche of papers regarding this issue have being published in the last years [2]. Great efforts are being made to optimize cleaning strategies to reduce the high operation and maintenance costs in solar power plants. Besides optimized cleaning, another mitigation strategy could be to reduce the dust accumulation rate by using AS application on the solar surfaces (reflectors and receivers). Both strategies are two of the concepts that are being studied to reduce the water consumption in CSP plants within the Horizon 2020 WASCOP project [3]. The study of natural soiling is necessary to determine the optimal cleaning procedure. The soiling process is a very complex problem due to the numerous influencing factors playing on it [4]. Environmental parameters (e.g. dust concentration, relative humidity, wind speed and direction), surface properties (e.g. porosity, surface tension, temperature) and site and installation characteristics (e.g. orientation, height, inclination angle) play a role in the particle adhesion. In the present work, AR coated borosilicate samples were outdoor exposed at Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA) in a special rack that allows the evaluation of soiling at different inclination angles and orientations. In addition, a hydrophobic AS treatment was applied in half of the samples to study its effect. The methodology and the obtained results are presented and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Sample Preparation

Borosilicate glass samples of 100 x 100 mm² and 3 mm thickness were coated with a sol-gel AR coating in both sides of the glass. This AR coating, based upon the CIEMAT patent [5], was deposited by Archimede Solar Energy (ASE) with its industrial deposition machine. After that, a hydrophobic commercial AS coating (ClearShield Eco-System™) was applied in half of the samples by rubbing the area with a cotton cloth wetted with the commercial solution. Figure 1 shows a schematic view of the sample configuration as well as a photo of one of the samples before testing.

FIGURE 1. Scheme of the testing samples (left) and photo of one of the samples before testing (right).

Study Methodology

14 samples were installed in a special exposure rack previously used for mirror studies. This rack is sited at Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA) which has climatological conditions typical from semi-arid and semi-desert areas. Samples were placed at different orientations (north, south, east and west) and for each orientation three different inclination angles (45°, 90° and 135°) were also tested. Moreover, one sample was placed at 0° in southwest orientation and another one at 180° at northeast orientation. The test began in March 2018. Figure 2 shows a photograph of the samples placed in the exposure rack.

FIGURE 2. Exposure rack used in the outdoor exposure study with the glass samples.

After each month of exposure, samples were collected from the rack and they were characterized by visual inspection, measuring the hemispherical transmittance and also the static contact angle. Then the samples were exposed again, without any artificial cleaning, until the next month.

Hemispherical transmittance spectra of the samples were measured at the wavelength range of 300-2500 nm. The equipment used was a UV/VIS/NIR Perkin-Elmer LAMBDA 950 double beam spectrophotometer with a 150-mm diameter Spectralon® coated integrating sphere. The solar hemispherical transmittance ($\tau_{s,h}$) was calculated by averaging the transmittance data over the direct AM1.5 solar spectral irradiance given by the current standard ASTM G-173-03, following the IEC62862-1-1 standard as it is expressed in equation 1.

$$\tau_{s,h}(300,2500) = \frac{\int_{300}^{2500} \tau_{\lambda,h}(\lambda) G_b(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_{300}^{2500} G_b(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (1)$$

Where $\tau_{\lambda,h}(\lambda)$ is the spectral hemispherical transmittance and $G_b(\lambda)$ is the spectral direct solar irradiance.

Water static contact angle (WCA) measurements were performed with a KSV CAM 200 instrument. These measurements denote the effect of the AS treatment on the surface of the samples, by measuring if the hydrophobicity is maintained over the testing time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The application of the AS treatment implies modifying the surface tension of the AR sample but also decreasing a little the solar transmittance. In fact, the initial solar transmittance of the AR coated glass varied from an average value of 0.974 to an average value of 0.970 after applying the AS treatment. Regarding the surface, the application of the AS treatment, modified the WCA from around 44° to around 95°. Photographs of the water droplets on the surface before and after the AS treatment are shown in Figure 3. When higher WCA are achieved, higher is the decrease in solar transmittance. This is due to the modification in the pore structure that increases the AR refractive index value.

FIGURE 3. Photographs of the water droplets obtained in the static water contact angle (WCA) measurements in the AR sample surface (a) and in the AS/AR sample surface (b).

During outdoor exposure in the experimental site, it was found the important role played by the inclination angle in soiling phenomena. As lower is the angle with the horizontal, as higher is the sample soiling. It can be seen in Figure 4, the pictures corresponding to samples after four months exposed at 0° , 45° , 90° , 135° and 180° . It should be noted that this measurement corresponds to August, when more dust and less rainfall are present. In these pictures is clearly seen that the highest degree of soiling occurred to the sample exposed horizontally and it became lower as increase the inclination angle. In fact, the solar transmittance decreased around 6 percentage points for the sample place horizontally meanwhile this decrease was around 1-2 percentage points for the samples place at 135° or 180° (see Table 2). This tendency was observed for all the exposure orientations, and the differences among the different inclination angles are more remarkable when more soil deposition happened. So, differences in solar transmittance with the inclination angle were lower during autumn or winter. Moreover, for all the inclinations, the climatic parameters also affected the soiling, observing more soiling deposition during the summer.

FIGURE 4. Visual aspect of samples exposed for 4 months at different inclination angles.

With regards to the AS treatment, Figure 5 presents the photographs of samples exposed for 2 months at three different inclination angle, where it can be clearly seen the two zones of the sample with and without the AS coating. The left half side corresponds to the AR coated glass meanwhile the right half side corresponds to the AS/AR coated glass. The application of this AS treatment affects to the dust adhesion. In the AS zone the soil is accumulated in small areas and the fine dust is less adhered. This fact was also observed for samples artificially soiled with sand in a previous research [6]. In Table 1 the normalized solar transmittance values measured for these three samples in both zones of the samples are recorded, considering 1 the initial value of each sample before testing. As it can be observed, the sample placed horizontally decreases its solar transmittance to a larger extent than the others due to the soiling, as it was also observed in Figure 4. On the other hand, it can be remarked for the three samples that after two months of exposure, the AS treatment is working properly and the decrease in solar transmittance by soiling is lower in the sample zone with the AS coating. It should be taken into account that the initial value of solar transmittance is slightly lower for the AS coated zones and then this not necessary means that the solar transmittance values are higher for the soiled AS/AR part than for the soiled AR part.

FIGURE 5. Pictures of samples after two months of outdoor exposition at different inclination angles, 0° (left), 45° (center) and 90° (right).

TABLE 1. Normalized solar transmittance values for samples located at different inclinations after 2 months

Sample	0°	45°	90°
AR zone	0.956	0.986	0.987
AS/AR zone	0.969	0.984	0.993

During the experiment, it was detected some issues that it is necessary to take into account to design further tests. Contrary to what occur in the case of reflectors experiments, the soiling of the back side could affect to the transmittance measurements in glass samples, distorting the measurement results. This soiling does not occur in real operating conditions where the glass tubes are exposed to soiling only in one side (the external side of the glass tube). The solar transmittance values obtained before and after cleaning the back side of the samples after being exposed 4 months are recorded in Table 2. As it can be seen, the effect of cleaning in the solar transmittance for samples placed at inclination angle of 0° and 45° is null or small, but it became important for higher inclination angles. Therefore, the effect of the back side soiling depends on the inclination angle, being more important for higher inclination angle. On the other hand, the variation of the solar transmittance values with the inclination angle after removing the effect of the back side soiling demonstrate the soiling dependence of the inclination angle in accordance with the pictures showed in Figure 4.

TABLE 2. Solar transmittance values for samples exposed for 4 months, measured as they were collected from the rack and after cleaning the back side with a wet cloth. These data correspond to the AR coated zone.

	0°	45°	90°	135°	180°
As collected	0.916	0.912	0.944	0.945	0.888
After back side cleaning	0.916	0.919	0.950	0.953	0.960

After evaluating the effect of the back side soiling in the transmittance measurements, it was thought that the design of the exposure rack was not the adequate for testing glass samples. Glass samples should be exposed in a way that the back side soiling was not produced. It could be either by covering the back side to avoid its soiling or by cleaning properly the back side before measuring the transmittance. In our case, the second solution was adopted to continue the test as the fixing elements in the rack were not designed to fix thicker samples. From these results, both sides of all the samples were cleaned with water and a cotton cloth in order to reset and to go on the study minimizing the effect produced by the back side soiling. In Figure 6 it is presented the normalized solar transmittance values measured for all the samples after cleaning both sides, considering 1 the initial value of each sample before testing. As it can be seen, the initial values are not completely recovered in any case with the cleaning method used, although values very close to the initial values were achieved. It should be noted that no artificial cleaning was performed during 4 months of exposure. Furthermore, it was observed that in 10 samples from 14, the zone with the AS treatment recovered more than the zone without the AS treatment. These results suggest that the hydrophobic treatment make easier the surface cleaning.

FIGURE 6. Normalized solar transmittance of all the samples after cleaning both sides with water and a cotton cloth.

With respect to the effect of sample orientation on soiling, the comparison of the results did not show differences in soiling. It is important to say that the samples were exposed at height of 0.7 m and at this height the low wind speed is insufficient to create variations. Test at higher heights should be done to properly evaluate this effect.

During the test, some samples were soiled by birds' dirt and as it can be expected samples soiled in this way are placed horizontally or at 45°. Pictures of a sample soiled in this way during different exposure times are presented in Figure 7 to observe the evolution. The bird dropping fell after 6 months of exposure, and the next month the spot was reduced by natural cleaning. Finally, three months later the spot was completely removed. This exposure time corresponds to April 2019, when high rainfall was registered at PSA (Figure 8).

FIGURE 7. Pictures of evolution of bird droppings in a sample exposed.

FIGURE 8. Registration of rainfall during the 6-9 months of outdoor exposure.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the effect of some parameters on soiling of AR coated glass was studied. The inclination angle showed an important influence in the soiling deposition, being the higher soiling deposition when lower is the inclination angle. In addition, it was found that the application of a AS treatment influences in the soiling behavior and helps to clean the soiled surface. The design of the experiment was optimized by removing the soiling of the back side of the samples, which is not realistic under real operating conditions. The natural cleaning produced by rainfall was able to dissolved organic soiling due to the birds.

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